

**DEVELOPMENT OF POTENTIAL TOURISM IN RATNAGIRI DISTRICT
OF KONKAN REGION****Dr. Prakash J. Hajare***Assistant Professor, Abasaheb Marathe Arts & New Commerce,
Science College, Rajapur (Ratnagiri), Maharashtra**Corresponding Author: Dr. Prakash J. Hajare***DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.13909776****ABSTRACT:**

The Ratnagiri district, located in the Konkan region of Maharashtra, boasts a rich natural beauty, cultural heritage, diverse ecosystems, and pristine landscapes that offer immense potential for tourism development. This paper explores the various dimensions of tourism potential in Ratnagiri, including natural attractions, historical sites, local culture, and culinary offerings. Positive publicity, minimum basic infrastructural facilities, amenities, and mostly the tourism products are focus and highlighted for the development of tourism in Ratnagiri district. Transportation plays a vital role in tourism development. Road construction of National Highway 66 has been going on for the last 14 years under the supervision of the State Road Board. Today finally the roads are not ready so tourists go directly to Sindhudurg district using National Highway No. 48. Therefore, Ratnagiri district is excluded. Also, some tourist centers are potentials and waiting of tourists due to lack of service facilities. The paper will also analyze existing tourism infrastructure, and recommend strategies for sustainable tourism development that benefits both the local economy and environment.

Keywords: *Ratnagiri, Tourism Development, Konkan Region, Sustainability, Cultural Heritage*

INTRODUCTION:

The Konkan region, stretching along the western coast of India, Konkan region is a great treasure of tourism with trove of natural beauty, cultural heritage, and historical significance. In Konkan Region there were five districts viz Palghar, Thane, Raigad, Ratnagiri and Sindhudurg. The district boasts of scenic beaches, hills, waterfalls, religious and culturally importance and making it an ideal destination for tourists seeking a unique blend of

nature and culture. In this study, we aim to identify potential areas of tourism development in Ratnagiri district. Ratnagiri district is a waiting to be explored. Despite its rich potential, but due to limited infrastructure and lack of awareness among tourists and lack of publicity. The district's proximity to the Arabian Sea and its rugged terrain have created a unique blend of marine and hill attractions, offering endless opportunities for adventure and relaxation.

However, the tourism sector in Ratnagiri district is still in its infancy, with few tourists' infrastructure and services available. The district's tourism industry is characterized by small-scale, informal enterprises, with limited capacity to cater to the growing demand for tourism services. This lack of infrastructure and services has hindered the growth of tourism in the region, resulting in a significant loss of revenue and potential economic benefits. Despite these challenges, there is a growing recognition of the potential of tourism in Ratnagiri district as a tool for economic development and sustainable growth. The district's rich cultural heritage, diverse natural beauty, and historical significance make it an attractive destination for tourists seeking unique experiences. Moreover, the government's initiatives to promote tourism in the region have created a favorable environment for investment and development.

This research paper aims to explore the potential of tourism in Ratnagiri district of Konkan region and identify the key factors that can contribute to its development. The study will analyze the existing tourism infrastructure and services in the region, identify the gaps and challenges, and propose strategies for sustainable development of tourism in Ratnagiri district. The findings of this study will provide valuable insights for policymakers, investors, and

entrepreneurs seeking to develop the tourism industry in Ratnagiri district and promote sustainable economic growth in the region.

PRIMARY OBJECTIVES:

1. To identify and analyze the existing tourism resources and potentialities in Ratnagiri district of Konkan region.
2. To assess the availability of tourism infrastructure and services in the district.
3. To investigate the impact of tourism on the local economy and community in Ratnagiri district.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

The present paper is based on primary and secondary data. Primary data has been collected through field visit, observations conducting observational studies of tourist destinations and activities in Ratnagiri district to gather data on infrastructure, amenities, and services. and interview with tourists and community to collect information related to tourism development from the point of view of their perspectives and experiences. Secondary data collected from published and unpublished books, magazines, papers etc.

STUDY REGION:

Ratnagiri district is one of the 36 districts of Maharashtra. It is located on

the Konkan strip of the west coast of India. The geographical location of the district is lies in between 16.30° north latitude and 73.53° east longitude. It's bounded by the Arabian Sea to the west, the Sahyadri hills to the east, the Raigad district to the north, and the Sindhudurg district to the south. The eastern part of the district is covered by basalt and has been heavily eroded by the high rainfall and undulating topography. Ratnagiri district is a coastal region located in the Konkan division of Maharashtra, India. The district is known for its rich natural resources, including its coastline, mountains, and rivers. Despite its natural beauty and economic significance, the district has been experiencing rapid population growth and urbanization in recent years. This study aims to analyze the demographic characteristics of Ratnagiri district using geographical analysis.

The eastern part of the region mainly comprises of the Sahyadri Range and its sloping mountains adjoining the Konkan plain. On the western side is a hilly landscape. The topography of this region is highly uneven. In this area you will find extremely narrow riverine plains adjoining the coastline. About eighty five percent of the area comprises of hills. Due to its shallow nature the coastline is hardly used for navigation.

EXISTING TOURISM DESTINATIONS:

Ratnagiri district is covered by 8208 sq.km. There were nine tehsils in Ratnagiri district. Each and every tehsil having tourism potential. Due to lack of infrastructural facilities all are awaiting. At present 22 existing tourism places in Ratnagiri district. Out of them, some tourism places are developed like Ganpatipule temple and beach, Pawas, Thibaw Palace, Pawas, Guhagar beach, Veas beach, Mondovi beach, and Marine Aquarium & Museum. Rest of them are also potential tourism destinations it included all forts also.

Beaches:

1. Ganpatipule Beach: A popular beach known for its serene surroundings and scenic beauty.
2. Pandre Samudra: A secluded beach with crystal-clear waters and picturesque views.
3. Ratnagiri Beach: A scenic beach with a historic lighthouse and a temple.
4. Velas Beach: A quiet beach with clear waters and a scenic view of the surrounding hills.
5. Guhagar Beach: A popular beach with a historic temple and scenic views.

Potential Tourism Destinations:

There is great scope for the development of infrastructure, but lack of funds and initiatives most of the tourism destinations are in potential category. Not only the infrastructure but also the publicity, leadership of local

authorities, NGOs, MTDC and tourism organization in Ratnagiri district.

Historical Places:

1. Ratnagiri Fort: A historic fort built by the Portuguese in the 17th century.
2. Purnagad Fort: Purnagad Fort is a name to be reckoned with. Purnagad fort is situated on the top of a mountain and is known for very strong construction.
3. Ambolgad Fort: The fort of Ambolgad was primarily built to keep an eye on the ancient port of Musakaji and the surrounding seas. Col. Imlock captured this fort for the British in 1818. The residential portion of Ambolgad was shifted out completely by 1862.
4. Gopalgad Fort / Anjanvel Fort: This fort is an important fort in Ratnagiri district. The Fort is located on a prominent and commanding point for guarding the trade route along the Vashishti River.

Beaches:

1. Aare Ware Beach: Aare-ware Beach is only about 12 km from the famous Ganpatipule Temple. These twin beaches, Aare-Ware, were formed by a mountain corner submerged in the sea.
2. Kasheli Beach: It is located in Kasheli village of Ratnagiri district, Maharashtra. Ratnagiri district offers the most diverse

attractions for tourists in the form of most beautiful beaches, historical monuments and serene temples.

3. Mirya Beach: This beach is located near Ratnagiri city. Mirya beach offers a healthy marine life up for exploration.
4. Nevare Beach: This beach is situated between Ganpatipule and Ratnagiri. Clean and peaceful beach.

Religious Destinations:

1. Dhutpapeshwar Temple: Nature has freely poured its treasures on Rajapur. Very close to Rajapur town, at a distance of 1 km, in the dense forest, the temple of Dhutpapeshwar is situated in numerous chains of small and big waterfalls of Mridani River beside the Temple.
2. Sri Kanakaditya Temple: This temple is located 1.4 km away from Kasheli beach. It is one of the few temples in Maharashtra dedicated to the Sun God.
3. Mahakali Temple: At a distance of 3 km from the Kankaditya temple of Kasheli, there is an awakened temple of Mahakali in Adivare village.
4. Rajapur Ganga: The Ganga of Rajapur is the subject of study by many scholars. The Ganges has suddenly appeared. This place since a time immemorial and is considered to be a geological

wonder. This place is located nearby Rajapur town.

Other Tourism Destinations:

1. Unhale Hot Water Spring: Unhale Hot Water Spring is situated in the village of Unhale near the town of Rajapur.
2. Rock Carvings / Katal Shilp: The Greek word petroglyph means carving on a rock; it is equally applicable to sculptures carved on a hard rock about 10,000 years ago by primitive man in the Konkan. This place is located at Dhartale village in Rajapur.

CONCLUSION:

The Ratnagiri district of Konkan region has immense potential to develop tourism industry, which can lead to significant economic growth and socio-cultural development. This study has identified various tourist attractions and activities in the district that can be leveraged to attract visitors. The findings of this study suggest that the development of tourism infrastructure, such as hotels, restaurants, and transportation facilities, is crucial to support the growth of tourism in the region. Moreover, the promotion of local culture and traditions through festivals and events can enhance the overall tourist experience.

The implementation of effective tourism policies and strategies by the

government and local authorities is essential to ensure the sustainable development of tourism in Ratnagiri district. This study has highlighted the potential of Ratnagiri district in Konkan region to develop its tourism industry. By leveraging its natural attractions, cultural heritage, and adventure activities, the district can become a popular tourist destination, generating economic benefits and promoting socio-cultural development.

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